

DEVELOPING A PROBLEM-SOLVING MODULE IN MATHEMATICS FOR HIGHLY-ABLE POST-PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Even with the introduction of a new mathematics syllabus at post-primary-level in Ireland, there has been ongoing doubt raised as to the effectiveness of our mathematics education for highly-able students. Prior research has indicated the use of problem-solving and open-ended questioning as important tools in students' mathematical development. This paper discusses the design of a module for post-primary students using these methods.

INTRODUCTION

Research has emphasised the importance of problem-solving in the study of mathematics, as well as its ability to develop students' higher-level thinking skills (Lewis & Smith, 1993; Shen, 2012). The introduction of Project Maths, the latest approach to teaching and learning mathematics at post-primary level in Ireland, has meant a renewed focus on problem-solving in the classroom (NCCA, 2013). In relation to highly-able students, teachers face the difficult task of differentiating their lessons to try to cater for such students, with teachers citing reasons such as overloaded curricula, large class sizes, and an emphasis on catering for weaker students as some of the reasons why it was not always possible to support highly-able students (Riedl Cross, Cross, O'Reilly, & Mammadov, 2014). Problem-solving, together with open-ended questioning, allows highly-able students to explore topics further, investigating various approaches and depth within a problem, creating a rich learning experience for these students (Hmelo-Silver, 2004; Kwon, Park, & Park, 2006). Otherwise, out-of-school programmes such as the Centre for Talented Youth, Ireland (CTYI) (<https://www.dcu.ie/ctyi/index.shtml>), and mathematical enrichment programmes (e.g. <http://www.irmo.ie/>) provide opportunities to further their knowledge and skills in mathematics.

In this paper, we describe a problem-solving mathematics module developed for highly-able post-primary students. This module, run in conjunction with CTYI, aims to improve highly-able students' problem-solving abilities, while tracking their mindset and resilience throughout a fourteen-week programme, through standard tests and reflective diaries kept by the students throughout the programme. The results of these investigations are beyond the scope of this paper, and therefore we shall focus here instead upon the design and development of the module itself and the research underpinning its foundations.

BACKGROUND

Gifted Education refers to the strategies, techniques or programmes employed by schools, parents and educators to provide highly-able students with differentiated learning that meets their needs (Gallagher, 2003, pp. 17–21). The vast array of terms used to describe students within Gifted Education provides an insight into the often-fragmented nature of research in the area. “Gifted”, “talented”, “gifted and talented”, “highly-able” and “exceptionally-able” are just some of those used, with little consensus as to which one is best suited, or to whom

they refer. Traditional definitions of giftedness were based on IQ or standardised testing measures (Fasko, 2001; Sternberg, 1999), and debate remains as to whether this is a constant throughout a person's life. In recent decades, research has explored giftedness as a more complex issue, involving, for example, a wide range of intelligences (Gardner, 1999; Gardner & Hatch, 1989), or a person's ability to interact with their environment (Sternberg, 1984). Numerous studies have also highlighted the necessity to include potential within the discussion of giftedness (Subotnik, Olszewski-Kubilius, & Worrell, 2011).

The National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA, 2007, p. 7) in Ireland use the term "exceptionally able" for students "who require opportunities for enrichment and extension that go beyond those provided for the general cohort of students". Whilst this report was prepared as draft guidelines it remains the most recent definition to date regarding Gifted Education in Ireland. It estimates that 10-15% of students may be exceptionally able, but the exact requirements of qualifying students may vary greatly in different school contexts. With the introduction of Project Maths, some parties expressed fears that, although this change may benefit students as a whole, it may not prove sufficiently challenging for more able students (NCCA, 2012), with an apparent lack of attention paid to the needs of the highly-able student (DES, 2010). Although Ireland performed slightly above average in the PISA mathematics rankings since 2006 it finished below the OECD average in terms of students rated as top performers (those scoring at the highest two levels of PISA) (O'Reilly, 2014, p. 8). While the latest rankings have improved in terms of Ireland's highly-able students, with 15.5% performing at the top level (slightly above the OECD average of 15.3%), there is still work to do to further develop the abilities of these students (OECD, 2016, p. 5).

Although students thought to be highly-able may often be grouped to allow for easier differentiation within lessons, the differences in ability between these students may be complex (Gallagher, 2003). At the moment, students with learning difficulties in Ireland may be able to avail of additional teaching within a resource classroom setting, but highly-able students have no such additional support network (NCSE, 2013). Acceleration or enrichment classes, such as AP Potential in the United States, offer students the opportunity to further develop their subject knowledge in school (Schiever & Maker, 2003). Traditionally, approaches in Ireland have favoured differentiation in the classroom as opposed to acceleration of students (Riedl Cross et al., 2014). The Consortium of Institutions for Development and Research in Education in Europe (CIDREE, 2010) evaluated the preparedness of the Irish, Swiss and Dutch education systems to address the needs of highly-able students, and highlighted the effectiveness of enrichment activities and pull-out programmes in both the Dutch and Swiss systems. The report suggested that both the Dutch and Swiss systems offered more opportunities for students who show characteristics of high-ability.

Research into best practice in the teaching of highly-able students has noted that characteristics often associated with highly-able students seem to indicate that a problem-solving approach to learning is a highly effective tool in developing understanding. Sriraman (2003, p. 163) echoed findings from the 1980s (Burton, 1984), showing that highly-able students flourish when their attention is captured through the use of open-ended questioning.

Problem-based-learning (PBL) has been shown to be particularly effective with highly-able students as they are often highly motivated, with the confidence to attempt more difficult or challenging tasks (Hmelo-Silver, 2004). Stepien, Gallagher & Workman (1993) found that highly-able students who were taught through PBL outscored their traditionally taught counterparts in multiple-choice testing, while highly-able students in an action research study showed greater levels of skill retention under PBL than a traditional setting (Dods, 1997).

Problem-solving in mathematics

In 1945, Polya published his book ‘How to Solve It’ , becoming a prominent figure in the research of problem-solving in mathematics education (Polya, 1957). Polya developed a four-step approach to problem-solving: understand the problem; devise a plan - which involves applying some problem solving strategies; carry out the plan; and look back. Polya is credited as a key influence in the influential problem-solving book “Thinking Mathematically” (Mason, Burton, & Stacey, 2010), and the system suggested therein by Mason et al follows a very similar dynamic. Once again, an emphasis is placed upon reflection after solving, or attempting to solve, a problem. The four-step process created and publicised by Polya remains strongly relevant to mathematics education today.

MODULE DESIGN

The module nurtures students’ problem-solving abilities through open-ended problems in a collaborative learning environment (Gokhale, 1995), with students working in small groups throughout. These groups are randomly assigned at the start of the module and remain the same for the duration, with three/four students per group. The teacher, acting as a facilitator to learning, encourages dialogue within groups and utilises probing questions to promote understanding as students learn to communicate their reasoning (Hmelo-Silver & Barrows, 2006).

The module generally operates once a week, over a 3-hour period (a 2-hour class and 1-hour tutorial), where the final hour tutorial revolves around one designated problem that students must reflect on in the form of a diary entry. This practice is modelled on the final problem-solving step outlined by Polya (1957), and corroborated by Mason et al. (2010). Based on a combination of these models and observation of the processes taken by students in class, the model shown in Figure 1 was created to represent the path taken in problem-solving groups:

Figure 1 Problem-Solving Process

Where students have disproven a prior conjecture through critique, they return to the conjecture stage, and this movement between steps 2 and 3 may occur multiple times within a problem.

Problem-solving strategies provide students with a framework to approach mathematical problems (Katz, Segal, & Stupel, 2016). This project utilises several common strategies, and implements them as weekly themes, allowing students to discover them while solving problems. The themes for the first seven weeks are: visuals; patterns; specialising and generalising; conjectures; assumptions and questioning; structure; and working backwards. Problems chosen within each week emphasise the theme, although many problems utilise multiple strategies in their solution. Students are encouraged to find multiple ways to solve the problem by the facilitator, and thus can discover new strategies through inquiry. At the end of the tutorial the facilitator draws attention to the weekly theme so students are aware of future use of the strategy. The next four weeks focus on problems aligned to the four contextual strands of the Junior Cycle Mathematics: Number, Algebra and Functions, Geometry and Trigonometry, and Probability and Statistics (DES, 2017, p. 9). Problems during the remaining weeks are more general, following no contextual or strategical theme.

We will now look in greater detail at specific examples that the students meet in the module, and discuss typical reactions to these.

Example 1

In the first tutorial, under the theme “visuals”, students meet the question:

“How many squares are on a regular chessboard?”

(Mason et al., 2010, p. 17)

Students often begin this problem by drawing out a chessboard to help, as shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2 Regular Chessboard

Whilst this makes it possible to solve the problem, first exploring smaller versions of the pattern board will aid them in coming to this solution, as shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3 Specialised Chessboard Pattern

Developing a visual aid for the problem helps students with their problem-solving; however, within the above visuals we have also specialised the problem. Rather than continue to work with the next stage of the diagram, most students will begin to notice a pattern emerging, and thus find the answer and perhaps move on to generalise the problem. This emphasises the overlap of different strategies within each problem, and the facilitator ensures students recall this overlap as the module progresses.

The initial problem may be solved without too much difficulty, and so the facilitator is also responsible for pressing the students to explore the problem further. Students may determine an algebraic generalisation, but also display mathematical creativity in developing an extension to the problem. The creation of an extension allows students to take a problem which may not overly challenge them, and alter it to meet their own needs. Two examples of extensions to the problem have been to use a 3D model, or to seek the number of rectangles in a regular chessboard.

Example 2

The tutorial problem during week 5, under the theme “assumptions and questioning”:

25 coins are in a 5 by 5 array. A fly lands on a coin and wants to hop to every coin exactly once, at each stage moving only to an adjacent coin in the same row or column. Is it possible?

(Mason et al., 2010, p. 161)

Once more, a visual aid will provide an introductory strategy to this problem. This may take the form of a diagram, such as that in Figure 4, or by students using physical objects to represent the fly and coins.

Figure 4 Fly Hopping Routes

Students usually begin with an opening array of coins on which they can attempt to solve the fly's path, and then proceed to choose various 'starting coins' to show that it works. The common assertion at this point is that it works and they declare the problem solved. While they have utilised a visual aid to reach this conclusion, students often 'assume true' for all coins. This assumption leads to an incorrect solution, and thus students are encouraged to ask more questions of the problem, such as "does it matter what coin the fly lands on", or "what happens if I change the number of coins?", exploring the problem in greater depth.

CONCLUSION

A problem-solving approach to instruction has been well-researched in recent decades in the education of highly-able students (Schiever & Maker, 2003; Strobel & Van Barneveld, 2009). When students are encouraged to ask further questions about a problem, they begin to 'think mathematically' (Schoenfeld, 1992), and develop the intrinsic motivation to understand the inner-workings of a problem. The module discussed in this paper utilises the problem-solving approach in an environment designed to nurture students' problem-solving abilities and higher-order thinking skills. Schoenfeld (1992) outlined the role the learning environment plays in developing this mode of thought within students. Collaborative learning through group-work gives students the opportunity to communicate their mathematical reasoning, and discuss alternative views on a problem. The role of the facilitator is to aid the student in these processes by encouraging them, asking probing questions, and promoting the desire to understand "why" a problem may be solved. In the early weeks of this module, the facilitator takes a more central role in questioning, to probe students' understanding of a problem. As students grow accustomed to this approach, they begin to ask the question of themselves and one another, thus lessening the role of the facilitator from week to week, and enabling them to develop as independent problem-solvers. Problem-solving is at the forefront of the design of Project Maths, and thus this module fits well into the Irish context, and also offers highly-able students the opportunity for challenge.

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